

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of University of Illinois (2015): The Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED) (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/A47D51A9-6C5F-4BC4-827B-B310B083481E>

Abstract

The Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED) is a technology intensive dataset developed by the University of Illinois. It offers worldwide social, political and economic event data from a global archive of news reports covering the time period from January 1st 1946 to 2008 in the form of the two datasets “SPEED Global Random Sample (1945-2005)” and the “SPEED Liberia, Philippines, and Sierra Leone (1979-2008) data” as downloadable material from their website. The data was collected to provide insights into the dynamics of conflict across contexts, its evolution and how violent conflict can be anticipated and avoided in the future (1). Of the 62.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are 1.800+ events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data. The data review contains a link leading to the official Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED) website from which both the dataset and the codebook, as well as additional information are available as a free download.

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Data Review – The Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED)

The Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED) is a technology intensive dataset developed by the University of Illinois. It offers worldwide social, political and economic event data from a global archive of news reports covering the time period from January 1st 1946 to 2008 in the form of the two datasets "SPEED Global Random Sample (1945-2005)" and the "SPEED Liberia, Philippines, and Sierra Leone (1979-2008) data" as downloadable material from their website. The data was collected to provide insights into the dynamics of conflict across contexts, its evolution and how violent conflict can be anticipated and avoided in the future (1). There are six main categories within the dataset: political expression events, politically motivated attacks, destabilizing state acts, political reconfiguration events, mass movements of people and cataclysmic events with each of them having further sub-categories (1).

The core components enabling effective data collection for this large-scale dataset consist of (a) the global news archive, (b) the classification scheme, (c) the BIN module, (d) the EAT module, and (e) the EXTRACT module (1).

The global news archive used for this dataset was compiled by the University itself and consists of over 40 million news reports. Reports concerning the time period from 1946 to 2006 were compiled using the complete digitized historical archives of the New York Times and Wall Street Journal. However, since the coverage of these two agencies alone was deemed not international enough, microfiche and microfilm records of both the Foreign Broadcast Information Service (CIA) and the Summary of the World Broadcast (BBC) were added. Starting from 2006 the designed SEARCH program has been scanning over 5,000 news feeds in 120 countries multiple times each day, scraping relevant news reports and allowing the archive to grow continuously (1).

These reports were then sorted using the regulations of SPEED's classification scheme which includes events pertaining to societal stability, human rights, electoral integrity, the supremacy of law, the security of property rights, the viability of governmental checks and balances, and the government's economic role.

An archive this large requires automated techniques to identify relevant reports and then sort them into the above mentioned categories. In order to do this an automatic text categorization program by the name BIN was developed: "BIN uses statistically based algorithms based on key words, word correlations, and semantic structures to identify and categorize relevant reports. BIN generates statistical probabilities that a news report belongs to a particular category within the classification scheme." (1). If this probability is high enough, the report in question gets assigned to one or more categories. BIN was taught using thousands of human-categorized reports and has proven itself to have a false negative rate of only 1% (1).

After accurately assigning the news reports into SPEED's classification scheme using the BIN module, a large amount of text needs to be processed in order to extract relevant information. To facilitate this, the event annotation tool EAT was developed: "EAT employs a variety of computational procedures rooted in the field of natural language processing (NLP) to highlight text that contains relevant information about events belonging to a specific event ontology." (1) This module too was trained using data coded by humans to teach it what type of information is considered relevant (1).

As its name indicates the EXTRACT module was designed to extract the information established as relevant using the prior modules. It contains multiple modules to extract information efficiently and accurately such as: (a) the calendaring module which focuses on the date an event occurred, (b) the geocoder module which identifies an events location, (c) the chaining technologies which make it possible to link related events that are contained in different news reports, and (e) the NLP techniques used to capture the identity of both event participants and external facilitators/collaborators (1).

"Within SPEED, event data is generated by human analysts using a suite of sophisticated tools to implement carefully structured and pretested protocols. These protocols are category-specific electronic documents that are tailored to the information needs of a particular category of events." (1) These protocols include over 350 queries, though they are highly branched with 97% of the queries being response activated. They are however designed to provide event-specific information on the following factors:

- "Who
 - Initiators; Targets/Victims
 - International involvement
- What
 - Event type
 - Impacts (people, property, society)
 - Consequences (for initiators)
 - Reactions (to event)
 - Subsequent events
- How
 - Weapon, modes of expression, type of natural force
- Where
 - Geo-spatial location, geo-physical setting
- When
 - Date
- Why
 - Societal context
 - Attributed origins" (1)

For an exhaustive list of the coded variables please refer to the SPEED codebook.

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Armenia	59
Azerbaijan	105
Belarus	18
Estonia	14
Georgia	121
Kazakhstan	15
Kyrgyzstan	30
Latvia	31
Lithuania	45
Moldova	12
Russia	1117
Tajikistan	16
Turkmenistan	3
Ukraine	73
Uzbekistan	47

Sources:

- (1) The Social, Political and Economic Event Database Project (SPEED). <https://clinecenter.illinois.edu/project/human-loop-event-data-projects/SPEED>. Last accessed 30.09.2024.